

Research Article

The Influence of Parental Background on the Academic Performance of Children in Some Selected Secondary Schools in Kachia Local Government Area of Kaduna State

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Abstract

This study examined the influence of parental background on the academic performance of children in some selected Secondary Schools in Kachia area of Kaduna State. The Population consisted of 972 respondents. A sample size of 100 Senior Secondary Schools (SSS) 1, 2 and 3 students was randomly selected. Three research questions and three hypotheses were adopted and tested for the study. To determine the extent of significant relationship that existed between the independent and dependent variables at 0.05 alpha levels. Chi-square (X^2) was employed to analyze the data and reliability of the instrument. The result revealed positive relationship between parents socio economic status, educational status, parents level of income, family size and students' academic performance. Based on this finding, it was recommended that parents should improve on their level of Socio economic status, endeavor to control their family size, government should equip the schools with modern facilities, teachers should use good teaching methods, teaching aids and guidance and counseling department should be established in all schools.

Keywords: Parental Background, Socio-economic Status, Academic Performance, Children, Secondary School

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Introduction

From the beginning, parents have been the major persons involved in raising children in every society. That is why the family is recognized as an important agent of Socialization.

Adakeye (2002) that it is mainly through their efforts and abilities that children are socialized to become productive citizens. So, wherever parents possess the resources and skills and apply them effectively and joyfully in raising their children and the entire society benefits. This brings joy and pride to the nation, and encourages development and peaceful co-existence. The children themselves, feels good and bring happiness to their parents and the whole community.

In view of this, the influences of parental background, on the academic performance of children becomes an indispensable factor in the wheel of progress. It is a fact that parental background influences children academic performances either positively or negatively. A well to do family will have positive interest in the education of their children. According to Ezewu, (2003) family background of parents affects children especially in respect to their academic achievement.

Background of the Study

The influence of parental background on academic performance of secondary school children did serve as stepping stone or background to every individual in achieving educational goals. All the basic educational advancement of children lies in the hands of their parents.

Parent's socio economic condition, which includes parent's academic and professional affiliation, is also associated with academic gain of students. The results of many studies (Pedrosa, 2006 and Jeynes, 2002) confirmed the academic achievement of students is contingent upon parent's socio-economic condition. So the students belonging to higher social economic backgrounds, "Social and economic status of student is generally determined by combining parents' qualification, occupation and income standard" (Jeynes, 2002) Among many research studies conducted on academic achievement, it is not very surprising to observe that socio-economic status is one of the main elements studied while predicting academic performance.

Pedrosa *et al.* (2006) in their study on social and educational background pointed out those students who mostly come from deprived socio-economic and educational background performed relatively better than others coming from higher socio-economic

and educational area. They named this phenomena educational elasticity. It is obvious and true that the criteria for categorizing Socio-economic standard in different countries are different depending of norms and values. The criteria for low socio-economic status for developed country will be different from the criteria of developing nations and some will be in case of developing countries. "The total income of families, monthly or annually and their expenditures also put a great effect on the learning and academic opportunities accessible to youngsters and their chances of educational success.

Furthermore, they also pointed that due to residential stratification and segregation, the students belonging to low income backgrounds usually attend schools with lower funding levels, and this situation reduce achievement motivation of the students and high risk of educational malfunction in future life endeavors" (Escare, 2003).

Kwesiga (2002) approved that performance of students is also influenced by the school in which they studied but he also said that number of facilities a school offers usually determine the quality of the school, which in turn affect the performance and accomplishment of its students and argued that working class homes are usually associated with overcrowding; and children from overcrowded homes are usually deprived of quietness, privacy and good health environment which often do not allow for a healthy living. They added that, such conditions exposes children of working class to different types of diseases and illness, which contributes to their irregular attendance at school, lack of concentration, tiredness and other weaknesses all of which correlate negatively to school success.

The family has the potential to influence a child's academic performance. This is because it is the first environment of the child. The initial experience that would mould the child's values, aspirations, emotions, interest and attitudes are offered by the parent/family. It is concluded that the type of schools in which students' studies greatly influence the educational performance and academic achievement of the students.

Statement of the Problem

The influence of parental background, that is, the socio-economic status of parents in the academic or achievement of their children have been posing very serious problem to many people in our society, which need investigation.

Graetz (1995) conducted a study on socio-economic status of the parents of students and concluded that socio-economic background has great impact on student's academic performance, main source of educational imbalance among students and student's academic success contingent very strongly on parent's socio economic standard.

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Most parents do not know that they have a vital role to play in improving their children's academic performance. Most of the parents only buy textbooks for their children without monitoring the wards to know whether they are reading them or not. Also most of them are not even interested in providing educational materials for their children. The only thing they are after is to see the result of their children at the end of every term which turns out to be poor.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study.

1. What role does the socio-economic position of parent's play in the academic performance of the child?
2. How does the family structure in terms of monogamy, polygamy and size affect the academic achievement of students?
3. To what extend does the level of education, attitude of parents and guidance affects the academic performance of children?

Objectives of Study

The objective of this research is meant to examine the influence of parental background on academic performance of children in some selected secondary schools in Kachia of Kaduna State.

The objectives of this study include the following:

1. To establish the effects that one's parental background poses on the academic performance of the child.
2. To suggest possible solutions on how students from poor homes can get along in their educational pursuit.

Statement of Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated to guide the study:

1. There are no significant different between the academic performances of the students and their parental background.
2. There is significant difference between the academic performance of students and their parental background.
3. There is neither any significant difference between the academic performances of the students and their parental background.

Significance of the Study

This researcher work shall be of up most significance to three (3) categories of persons:

1. Curriculum/educational planners.
2. Teachers.
3. And of course parents/guidance it will be significant to curriculum or educational planners in that, it will help them in planning adequately for students from different homes.

In the same vein, it will enable the teachers to know that students are not solely responsible for their poor performance thereby creating an avenue for teachers to come to grips with some of the impact that parents background poses avail the teacher the opportunity to design a correction measure which if adhered to, would spur both the teachers and students to greater academic achievements. Over and above all, this study will serve as a challenge to parents to improving conditions of the homes, thereby propelling their child to greater heights.

Scope and Limitation of the Study

This study was carried out in some selected secondary schools in Kachia, Kaduna State.

These schools include:

- 1 GSS Kachia Senior
- 2 GSS Kachia Urban
- 3 GSS Gumel Senior
- 4 GSS UngwanAtte
- 5 GSS KurminMazuga

The investigation covered SSS 1-3 using at least five (5) students randomly selected from each of the classes in the different schools so selected.

The study was limited by the difficulty in getting accurate information from students as some of the students gave limited details about their homes and parents background.

Secondly the research was limited by time as the time frame to turn in this study was too short to accomplish a more detailed research.

Thirdly financial limitations made the research to be restricted to few schools within the locality of the research and so the findings and outcome of the research may not provide an authoritative basis for necessary intervention.

Operational Definition of Terms

Influence

- The effect that somebody has on the way a person thinks behaves or acts.
- The power to affect, control or manipulate something or someone, the ability to change the development of fluctuating things such as conduct, thoughts or decisions.
- An action exerted by a person or thing with such power on another to cause change.
- A person or thing exerting such power or action.

Parents: These are father and mother of a child or guardian that normally takes care or hold responsibilities of a person at home. This refers to the one who has begotten offspring or occupies the role of mother or father.

Background: The cultural or social environment in which a person was brought up or has lived. This refers to traits of one's family it can also be seen as a family way of life. An information that is essential to understanding a situation or problem. It is also a state of the environment in which a situation exists.

Academic Performance: Is the extent to which a student, teacher, or institution has achieved their short or long term educational goals.

Children: Young people below the ages of puberty (18 years) or person strongly influence by the parents. They are persons who have not attained maturity or the age of legal majority. They refer to the beneficiaries of parental involvement, a heterogeneous population of predominantly school-aged.

Secondary School: Is an organization that provides educational instruction for students during the period from ages 11-18 years. These are between elementary school and college. That is offering general, technical, and vocational or college preparatory courses. It is a final stage of secondary education preparing for tertiary education or providing skills relevant to employment, usually with an increased range of subject options and streams.

Literature Review

Different authorities from the field of psychology and sociology have made immense contributions in such, scholars have established the fact that the socio-economic class which one's parent belongs to influences the child overall performance.

James and Dimitriy, (2007) has focused on the effects of parental background on such outcome for their children as cognitive skills, education, health and subsequent income. There is little doubt that economic status is positively correlated across generations. Parents and the family environment in general, have important impacts on behavior and decisions taken by adolescents. There is also the belief that there is a strong link between parent's social class and their children's school achievement. The differences could be traced to the type of occupation in which one is engage which could also determine to a great extent, one's income and ability to provide enough funds and optional facilities which a growing school child requires for high performance at school.

Carneiro and Heckman (2003) opined that current parental incomes does not explain a child's educational choice but family fixed effects such as parental education levels that involves permanent income, and much more positive role. Positive attitude to school will themselves attained a high level of Western education. While the father is away, it is expected that the mother takes care of the children at home and as such, the children are closer to their mother. Walker, (2005) educated mother, knowing the importance of education should as much as possible generate in the child interest and curiosity for education at an early age. With this, it is therefore necessary to agree with Mutran's (1980) view that children with more educated parents score higher than children from less education homes (or parents) on the intellectual curiosity which is positively associated with grades.

Okoh (1983) in his work say that students have shown that children from low income home come to school with two fold handicap.

Their innate intelligence is under developed in certain aspects that are important for success in present day educational systems and their personality is structured that they are not likely to do well in school. The child from the low social class according to these studies has not his spare time carefully organized for. He has a notion and is incapable of planning and pursuing long term projects. To such a child, luck, rather than vigorously planned work appears to be reason for success.

According to Rothesetin (2004) the social class of parents is fundamental condition to the individual's educational and vocational decisions. He went further to explain that social membership influence and which exert considerable influence on the individual include sex, family, age, race, culture, school and economy.

Farooq, Chaundhry, Sharique and Berham (2011) emphasized the social class of parent is a dominant factor in the academic performance. The academic abilities and socio-

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economic background of youth impose considerable constraints upon performance of students and on the type of vocation they can make. The child middle class family has a wider range of possibilities open to him than a child from a poor socio-economic class.

Occupation of parents, this involves the type of work or job done by the parents of these students. There are parents whose work does not give time for their children as such the students are affected negatively Duke (2000). Most time you discover that most students or children are influenced by the occupation of their parents doing, parental or family set standard may greatly affect performance of their children either positively or negatively even in the occupational choice of their children later in their lives and so motivated them to be achievement oriented. Thus, in a family where some particular careers are of great priority, tend to orient its children towards achieving that goal. In some families because the family head is a lawyer the children will want to be a lawyer or even doctors, nurse or teachers or accountants because their parents are one or have set such standard for them. Studies have shown that a child particular socio-economic inheritance may have a direct and important effect on the career open or attractive to him than does his physical inheritance.

The economic and occupational level of home affects the vocational goals of the youth by influencing their aspirations to be similar to those help by their parents and by Halsey, Health and Ridge (1980) discouraging aspirations to levels much above or below the parental occupational. The child's biological endowments in terms of personality traits are transmitted to him in form of genetic inheritance. If both parents possess high intellectual capabilities and transmit the traits for indigence to the child, that, child is very likely to be highly intelligent and benefit from education which will likely enhance his opportunity for occupations on the hand, a child of very low intellectual parents who inherited this traits may turn out to be an imbecile who may later find it difficult to be properly educated and be gainfully employed. So, the occupation of parents has a vital role to play in the lives of children. Halsey et al (1980).

Considine and Zappala (2002) quoted Sparkles (1999) showed that schools environment and teachers expectations from their students also have strong influence on student performance. Most of the teachers working in poor schools or schools having run short to basic facilities often have low performance expectations from their students and when students know that their teachers have low performance expectations from them, hence it leads to poor performance by the students.

Sentamu (2003) argued that schools influence educational process in content organization, teacher and teaching learning and in the end evaluation of the all. All

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these educationalists and researchers agreed with this principle that school put strong effect on academic performance and educational attainment of students.

Socio Economic Status of Parents and the Child Academic Performance

The socio-economic status in the traditional conceptualization consists of parental income, father's occupation, father education and occasionally, mother education. They also include other variables like household possessions and room in the household.

In the view child from a high socio-economic background has advantage over the child that is from a lower class. He supported this assertion by arguing that students from wealthy home have most infrastructural facilities such as television set, radio set, pictures, reading and writing materials at home. This material he says, tend to motivate them to learn at their own pace.

However, the situation is absolutely the reverse for children from poor home who due to the economic situation in the home are often devil good food, talk less of meaningful instructional materials. Following this same line of thought the lower the social class (opposition) of one's parents, less likely that can take advantage of educational opportunities.

Considine and Zappala (2002) also having the same views as Greatz (1995), in their study on the influence of social and economic disadvantage in the academic performance of school students noticed, where the parents or guardians have social, educational and economic advantage definitely strengthen the higher level success in future. But it is also noted that these parents make available sufficient psychological and emotional shore up to their children by providing good educational and learning environment that produce confidence and the improvement of skills needed for success.

Parents Income and the Child Education

While commenting further on the socio-economic problems she (Julian) explains that the income of parent also tends to affect a student educational performance. She lamented that:

"It is a natural phenomenon today for student who are from families when they can scarcely afford him or her food, Shelter and clothing to leave school as drop out' because of necessity. The incomes of parents do tell on the level of nutrition given to children. While explaining this further, she stated that if a growing child does not get enough satisfactory diet, physical and mental growth will be retarded:

“There is therefore no gain saying that learning and acquisition of knowledge depends mightily on whether or not the individual needs are met”. It is only for extend that the home is able to provide the necessities of life and atmosphere conducive to learning that the child is expected to learn. In the absence of experimental evidence, instruments have been used to identify income effects. John (2000) uses union status (occupation) as an instrument for parental income and so, assumes that unionized fathers are not more “able” parents than non -union fathers with similar observable skills, while uses variation in family income caused by state welfare rules, income sources and income before and after the education period of the child, as well as changes in income inequality. In both studies unanticipated changes were found in parental long run income, which have modest and sometimes negligible effects on the human capital of the children. However, John (2000) view in using union status as an instrument for income was accepted.

The Under Privileged and Over Privileged Children

In the contrary, over privileged children tends to perform even poorly than the unprivileged in some situation. Oladele (1981) confirmed that:

“In over privileged situation, the home is able to provide more than the minimum required for a good learning situation. The standard of living is quite high and the material comfort provided may be luxurious.

Children have all the necessary opportunity for education in the home, it is however very impossible that the child fails to make full use of these facilities if the family concentrates too much on its wealth and social position. The danger that the children from such family may think that they separate from others and this reason they fail to benefit fully from social interaction with other children at school” where these happens, the child becomes not only social burden to himself but also an anti-social figure to others. This privilege becomes a great disadvantage to himself and his family.

The Effect of Marital Status of Parents on Student Academic Achievements

It is a common knowledge that there are broken homes today than there will be in the past. This is a situation that is very unhealthy to the health development of the child. However, Peter and Sylvia (1955) stated that “a large percentage of maladjusted and delinquent children come from broken home. They have no play to follow, and so fall among the riff-raff it is obvious that in such homes, school cooperation is difficult to achieve. Besides, they the children lack necessary pace required for hard work”.

On the other hand, there is no doubt that polygamous home create an atmosphere of insecurity which may be good for children emotional and intellectual development. These set of children are often deprived of love and motivation by their parent-usually their father, because he has too many children from different mothers which he can conveniently carter for in terms of financing their education as well as providing other necessary materials needed for their schooling.

Because of this, he is compelled to choose a favourite among the children leaving the “care and maintenance” of the other children to their mother who may be poor and helpless in terms of finance. In addition to that, because of the family size, resulting from the kind of marriage size, resulting from the kind of marriage been practiced, he may not have time to effectively go through the school work of the children after school, because they are too many attending school, though not all may be privileged to attend school in some cases.

The Size of the Family

More so, it has been observed that the family size do affect the children overall performance of the child, the smaller the family size, the more likely the child tends to benefit from the parents. In his opinion, the most intelligent children emerge from smaller family in terms of size.

In such family, the child tends to be very close to the parents. Musgrave maintained that this can grant the child opportunity of being adequately catered for by the parents that is, the ability to communicate effectively.

Under types of family we are looking at whether, the children or child is born into a polygamous home or monogamous family and so on. The type of family which the students are born into can affect them either positively or negatively.

A child born by polygamous parents will find it very difficult to meet up with the financial demands of his school. Since there are a lot of children and wives to take care and as such the financial responsibility on the family will be very high such child will be affected negatively except the family is buoyant (Femi and Adewale, 2014).

Also even in a monogamous homes if the number of children in the family is large there will be great financial responsibility on the parents. The child may be affected negatively but if the number of children is reduced the parents will be able to meet their needs easily considering the family income. Also in families where the bread winner of the house is late (either the men or women).There will be high financial responsibility

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especially on our women if it was the man who died so, the children will be affected negatively and it will hinder their academic performance in the school (Anderson and Sullivan, 1998).

Parental Aspiration and Involvement in the Child's Education

Parent educational aspiration for their children and the extent to which a parental interest in their children education significantly impact the educational attitude and persistence of student. Pyong (1992) parental interest has been opionalised in two (2) ways. The amount of praise awarded to a student Reitzes and Muntran (2000) and monitoring of all the school experience and praise has a positive impact on students' grades and school monitoring has a positive effect on the class performance.

On his own part J.M.B. Douglas has shown that children whose parents are interested in their educational welfare tend to pull ahead of the rest; no matter the starting ability.

He says: The children who are encouraged in their work by their parent are, it seems at an advantage both in the relatively high scores they make in test and in the way they improve their scores between eight and eleven years" (38).

There is no doubt that parent attitudes help to condition children attitudes. A parent who shows a complete disregard for education, literacy, the niceties of social behaviour or any form of social advancement is bound to have some adverse effect upon his children's educational progress. Children need in a very real sense to be educated to appreciate education.

Parent Level of Education and Students Academic Performance

It is worth nothing that "parent" interest in their educational aspiration for their children cannot be female from their own personal education and cultural level. A well educated parent will hold in high esteem the education of their children. This will make them place more value parents place on education. The greater the likelihood the children are to pursue education. The more fatalistic parents are: the less likely children are to pursue education Ogbu (1995). Little wonder it is said that the child learns more from good parental example.

In the same, illustrated that there is measurable difference among student born to educated parents and the uneducated. He carried out a survey in some secondary school of Saudi Arabia which revealed that a good under school dropout where mainly from uneducated homes in which either one or both parents are otherwise blunt illiterate.

Parents' educational attainment is indicated by three highest levels of schooling, which the students' mother completed: primary, secondary and tertiary. These categories are defined on the basis of the International Standard classification of Education (ISCED, 2011). They posited that children brought up in less favourable conditions obtain less education despite the large financial returns to schooling for an extensive review (James and Dimitriy, 2007).

Summary

Children from enlightened home, stands the chance of benefiting from their parent's wealth of experience. Such children would in normal situation, have their note book crossed checked and sometimes helped in solving tough and difficult educational problems.

Great authorities from different fields agree on the fact that parent have a role to play in the child education, but how effective this role is being carried out depends to a very great extend or the level of enlightenment or education orientation the parent possesses.

Over and above all, going by the various contribution made by the different authorities (Scholars) it becomes more crystallized that the socio-economic background of parents possess a very strong influence on the student's performance overtime.

Methodology

This is specially written with the sole intentions of shedding light on the method and procedure used in conducting this research. In making sure that this intention is thoroughly achieved, the writers have therefore broken the method of study into various segments of discussion.

A wide range of research methods are used in Psychology. These methods vary by the sources of information that are drawn on, how those information are sampled, and types of instruments that are used in data collection methods qualitative data, quantitative data or both. (Strangor, 2007)

Research Design

The design used in this study was the descriptive survey design as it involves the collection of data to accurately between the parental background and academic performance of children.

According to Trochim (2005), research design provides the glue that holds the research project together.

Study Area

Kachia is one of the oldest local governments in Nigeria created during General Yakubu Gowon regime on 27th may, 1967. The local government further gave birth to four local governments area during different regimes, namely: ZangonKataf, Chukun, Kagarko and Kajuru Local Government areas.

The Local Government area shared boundary with the following Local Governments: Kajuru Local Government in the north East, Chukun in the North West, Kagarko in the South West, Jaba in the South and ZangonKataf in the East.

Kachia Local government has a good flat fertile lass mass, thick forest and mountains like any other savanna rain forest region. The Local Government area gets its rainfall from the month of April or there about to October with heavy down pour within the month of July and August. The inhabitants of the area include: Kadara, Jaba, Bajju, Gbagi and other tribes like the Hausas and Fulani.

The major economic activity of the Local Government Area is Farming. Apart from Kachia Township where the seat of the Local Government is situated, the rural areas are occupied by Farmers. These people grow crops like Maize, Guinea Corn, Millet, Rice, Cassava, Yam, Soya Beans, Ginger and others. Due to the high production of Ginger in the Local Government Area, Kaduna State Government built a Ginger Processing Company in Kachia town.

Population of the Study

The population of this study consisted of respondents from the selected senior school in Kachia area of Kaduna State. The respondents were drawn from SS1, SS2, and SS3 classes - (466 SS1 Students, 350 SS2 Students and 156 SS3 Students). The breakdown of the population used in this study is presented.

Table 1: Population of the Study

S/No	Name of Schools	SS1	SS2	SS3	Total
1	Government Secondary School Kachia	134	129	45	308
2	Government Secondary School Kachia Urban	120	60	23	203
3	Government Secondary School Gumel	120	90	30	240
4	Government Secondary School UngwanAtte	22	26	23	71
5	Government Secondary School Kurmin Mazuga	70	45	35	140
	Total	466	350	156	972

Table 2: Sample Size

S/No	Name of Schools	SS1	SS2	SS3	Total
1	Government Secondary School Kachia	10	10	5	25
2	Government Secondary School Kachia Urban	10	5	4	19
3	Government Secondary School Gumel	10	7	5	22
4	Government Secondary School UngwanAtte	5	5	4	14
5	Government Secondary School KurminMazuga	10	5	5	20
	Total	45	32	23	100

Sample Size and Sample Procedure

Stratified random sampling procedure was adopted to select the sample size of the population for the study. The sample size comprised 100 respondents (45 SS1 Students, 32 SS2 Students and 23 SS3 Students). The breakdown of sample size in this study is presented in the table two below.

Instrument for Collection of Data

This research was conducted mainly with the aid of a questionnaire. This questionnaire was designed with the aims and objective of the study in mind. The questionnaire was divided into various sections which asked information about the students' sex, age, class, and nature of school, general performance in school in their last promotion examination, parents' occupation, educational level, marital status and number of children of parents.

Method of Data Collection

The questionnaire contained sixteen numbers of items or questions the respondents were to respond to. The investigators personally administered the questionnaires to the hundred students that have been randomly selected from various schools. This was however done after a brief discussion with the students. They were meant to ensure the questions are filled during school hours in respective classroom after the researcher has successfully given them directives.

More so, they were fully informed that the purposes of the research personal identify and information would not be disclosed so as to avoid possible braised on their responses. The questionnaire were immediately collected from the students after they had successfully gone through the questions, ticking where necessary their response.

Data Analysis

The main statistical procedure employed in this study is Chi-Square statistics.

$$\text{KEY: } \chi^2 = \frac{E(F_o - F_e)^2}{F_e}$$

Data Analysis

The number of questionnaires administered to students (respondents) was one hundred. The result obtain will enable the researcher to verify the extent of the effect that one's parental standing posses on the child's education in terms of performance. In order to carry out a meaningful and comprehensive analysis, the responses were converted into raw scores and then to percentage. Also the data were tabulated in order for the information collected to be adequately summarized and explain easily.

However, the academic performance of students was presented as: above average (AA) Average (A) below average (BA).

Table 3: Sex Distribution of Respondents

Sex	SS1	SS2	SS3	Frequency	Percentage
Male	24	16	11	51	51
Female	21	16	12	49	49
Total	45	32	23	100	100

From the Table 3 and Fig 1, it means more males responded to the 100 questionnaires distributed, as 51 representing 51% respondents, while 49 representing 49% were female.

Table 4: Class Distribution of Respondents

Class	Male	Female	Frequency	Percentage
SS1	24	21	45	45
SS2	16	16	32	32
SS3	11	12	23	23
Total	51	49	100	100

Table 4 and Fig 2, analyzed that 45 students in SS1 responded to the questionnaires administered which is represented by 45%, in SS2 students responded, which represent 32 while SS3 23 students responded which represent 23% respectively.

Table 5: Academic Performance Distribution of Respondents

Students Performance	SS1	SS2	SS3	Frequency	Percentage
AA	20	16	15	51	51
A	19	13	6	38	38
BA	6	3	2	11	11
Total				100	100

The Table 5 shows that 51 students which are represented by 51% performed above average, 38 students represented by 38 performed within average while 11 students represented by 11% performed below average.

Research question 1:

What role does the Socio economic position of parents play in the academic performance of the child?

In order to examine the extent to which parents' performance income affects the child's academic performance question 9 and 10 of the questionnaire was designed. Parents whose occupation includes nursing, teaching (mainly Primary and Secondary School Teachers) and Civil Servant like Teacher was grouped among average income earners. In the same vein those whose occupation includes Medical Doctors, Engineering, Administrative Officers and their equivalent were grouped among the high income earners. However, those whose occupation includes Mechanic, Self sustaining Farmers, Traders and its equivalent were grouped among the low income earners.

Table 6: The percentage responses in respect to parents' level of income observed and expected frequency.

Parent level of income	SS1	SS2	SS3	Frequency	%	r-cal	r-cril
High income earners	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Average income earners	22	13	5	40	40		
	18	12.8	9.2				
Below income earners	23	19	18	60	60		
	27	19.2	13.8				
Total	45	32	23	100	100	1.8	5.99

Table 6 shows that 60% of students were from below average income parent's earners. 40% of students were from parents with average income earners.

In view of Table 8 it has proved that students who performed average were from parents with average income earners while students who performed below average were from parents with low income earners. In all practical respect, Table 8 demonstrates that the level of income of parents can affect the academic achievement of students.

Research Question 2:

How does the family structure in terms of monogamy, polygamy and size affect the academic achievement of students?

In order to verify if the marital status of parent's monogamy or polygamy poses any problem on the education of the students question 11 - 15 of the questionnaire were designed.

Table 7: The percentage of responses with respect to marital status observed and expected frequency.

Marital Status	SS1	SS2	SS3	Frequency	%	r-cal	r-cril
Monogamy	27	16	17	60	60		
	27	19.2	13.8				
Polygamy	18	16	6	40	40		
	18	12.8	9.2				
Total	45	32	23	100	100	3.18	5.99

In accordance with Table 7 it shows that 60% of students were from Monogamy homes while 40% were from Polygamy homes.

Reflect to Table 3, it can be seen that students from Monogamy homes tend to perform well (AA) in their academics while some students from Polygamy homes manage to perform within average (A) and others perform below average (BA).

This evidently explains that polygamy homes greatly affect the academic performance of students in a negative way.

Research Question 3

To what extent does the level of education, attitude of parents and guidance affect the academic performance of children?

In other to examine the extent to which the education qualification of Parents affects the academic performance of their children question 6 - 8 of the questionnaire was drafted.

More so, parents who have attained no formal education or have only attained primary or junior secondary education were grouped among the less educated persons.

Those who have attained Senior Secondary School Certificate, Teacher Grade II and their equivalent were grouped among those with average education, while those with B.Sc. BA, MA, PhD and their equivalent were grouped among those with higher education respectively.

Table 8: Percentage of responses with respect to parent level of education observed and expected frequency.

Parent level of education	SS1	SS2	SS3	Frequency	Percentage	r-cal	r-cril
High educated	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Average educated	7	12	7	26	26		
	11.7	8.32	5.98				
Less educated	38	20	16	74	74		
	33.3	23.68	17.02				
Total	45	32	23	100	100	4.87	5.99

The Table 8 shows that 26 respondents represented by 26% were from average educated parents while 74 respondents were from less educated parents.

However, column one (1) Table 3 was reflected for better analysis of the table. In reflect to Table 3 it proves that 51% of students who performed average were from average educated parents while who performed below average were from parents within or less education.

Consequently, this demonstrates that the higher the education of parents the more likely the child tend to perform better and brighter academically whereas the reverse can only be said of those students that are from no or less educated parents.

In all practical respect, Table 8 demonstrates that the level of income of parents can affect the academic achievement of students.

Research Hypothesis One

There is no significant difference between the academic performance of students and their parental background. The result in Table 4 depicts the calculated r between parents Socio economic background and students' academic achievement to be 1.8 and critical value of r is 5.99. The calculated statistically at $p > 0.05$ level of significance since

critical value is greater than the calculated r . (H_01) is thus rejected. This implies that significant relationship exists between parents Socio economic background and students' academic performance.

Research Hypothesis Two

Hypothesis two states that there is significant difference between the academic performance of students and their parental background. The result in Table 5 shows that the calculated r between family size and students' academic performance was 3.18 and the critical value of r was 5.99. Therefore, the calculated r is statistically significant at $p > 0.05$ level of significant since critical value is greater than calculated r . The hypothesis (H_02) is thus accepted, meaning that significant relationship exists between students, family size and students' academic performance.

Research Hypothesis Three

Hypothesis three states that there is neither any significant difference between the academic performance of students and their parental background. The result in Table 6 shows that the calculated r between the parents' educational background and students' academic achievement was 4.87 and critical value of r is 5.99. The calculated r is statistically significant at $p > 0.05$ level of significance since the critical value of r . The hypothesis (H_03) is rejected; the result now reveals that significant relationship exists between parents' educational background and students' academic achievement.

Summary of the Findings

This study was carried out to check the influence of parental background on the academic performance of children in some selected secondary schools in Kachia area of Kaduna State. Total of nine hundred and seventy two senior secondary schools students were drawn by sample random sampling from five schools. Three hypothesis and three research questions were stated to guide the study. Chi-square statistic (X^2) was used to analyze the data obtained.

After a careful analysis of the data gathered from the questionnaire administered to the various respondent on the topic under investigation it was revealed that:

The family structure, parent's occupation and educational level of parents have significant influence on the students' performance.

More than average students who performed excellently in their academic world were from average homes while poor homes on the other hand produced students who performed below average academically.

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The level of education of parents can determine the academic achievement of the child.

When there are many children in the home, the education of the child is seen as "Choice" and not as an obligation.

Children from broken home hardly perform above average academically due to the fact that parental involvement in the child's educational process is often lacking.

Children from poor homes can hardly buy their recommended textbook and as well pay their school fees.

Conclusion

Over and above all, we cannot over-emphasize the need to cater for the fallen standard of education in Nigeria as education remains the most viable and potent means of transformation of a society for a better one.

It is however evident from the foregoing chapters and pages of this study that the home which the child comes from affects his academic performance. The literature review has revealed that the home background of students has an impact on their academic achievement it has also revealed that the educational level of parents, the marital status, the parents level of involvement and participation in the child education, family size and of course level of income goes a long way to determine the academic performance of students.

Recommendation

In line with above findings on the study of the influence of parental background on academic performance of students, the following recommendations are therefore suggested.

1. Secondary education in Nigeria should be made compulsory and free at all levels and the government should equip public schools with modern infrastructure and facilities.
2. The Government should carry out an effective orientating programme which will be geared towards orientating parents about the need for them to be practically involved in their child's education.
3. The Teacher should endeavor to use such teaching methods and teaching aids that will cater for individual difference in the class and consider the less privilege before passing out instructions.

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4. Guidance and Counseling centers or departments should be introduced in all schools and the home should strive to provide an environment that is intellectually stimulating to the child.

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